

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 4 | OCTOBER - DECEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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Volume I, Issue IV | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“MANY A LIFE”

Some cry from jubilation,
Others cry from pain.
Some tears are of joy,
Others are in sorrow.
Some feast to celebrate birth,
Others feast to remember death.
Some travel to celebrate victory,
Others to bury defeat.
Some spend to extend life,
Others to end it.
Some die of overconsumption,
Others die of starvation.
Some live for legacy,
Others live for another day.
Some laugh,
Others wail.
Some are happy,
Others are sad.
Some in life,
Others in life.
Some, and others have many a life.

